

η^* -REGULAR AND η^* -NORMAL SPACES IN TOPOLOGY

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Abstract: In this paper, we introduce and study two new classes of generalized regular and normal spaces are called η^* -regular and η^* -normal spaces which are weaker than regularity and normality respectively. The relationships among strongly rg-regular, g-regular, regular, Q^* -regular, η^* -regular, almost regular and softly regular spaces are investigated. Some of basic properties and characterizations of η^* -regular spaces in the terms of some other separation axioms are obtained.

Key words: regular open, η^* -open sets; softly regular, almost-regular, Q^* -regular, η^* -regular spaces

2020 Mathematics subject classification: 54B05, 54B10, 54B15, 54D10

Received 26 Aug., 2025; Revised 02 Sep., 2025; Accepted 04 Sep., 2025 © The author(s) 2025.

Published with open access at www.questjournals.org

I. Introduction

In 1925, Urysohn [17] introduced and studied a new type of separation axiom, called Urysohn space. In 1926, Cartan [1] introduced and studied the concept of symmetric space. In topology, an R_0 -space is also known as a symmetric space. In 1937, Stone [16] introduced the notion of semi-regular spaces and obtained their characterizations. In 1958, Kuratowski [7] introduced a new type of generalized sets, called regularly-open and regularly-closed sets in general topology. In 1963, Levine [8] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets and obtained their properties. In 1969, Singal and Arya [14] introduced a new class of separation axiom (namely almost regular space) in topological spaces and investigated some basic properties with other separation axioms such as T_0 , T_1 , semi-regular, Hausdorff and k-spaces. In 1986, Munshi [10] introduced and studied some new class of separation axioms (named g-regular and g-normal spaces etc.) in topological spaces which are stronger than regularity and normality. In 1993, Palaniappan [12] introduced the concept of generalized closed sets, called regular generalized closed which is a weaker form of closed and g-closed sets and studied some properties. In 2010, Murugalingam and Lalitha [11] introduced and studied the concept of Q^* -open sets and obtained some properties of Q^* -open sets. In 2011, Gnanachandra and Thangavelu [3] introduced and studied the concepts of strongly rg-regular and strongly rg-normal spaces in topological spaces which are stronger than regularity and normality. In 2018, Kumar and Sharma [4] introduced and studied the concept of softly regular spaces in topological spaces which is a weak form of regularity and obtained some characterizations with regular, strongly rg-regular, weakly regular, almost regular, π -normal and quasi normal spaces. Recently, Hamant Kumar [6] introduced and studied the concept of Q^* -regular spaces which is a weaker form of regularity and obtained some characterizations.

II. Preliminaries

Throughout this paper, spaces (X, \mathfrak{T}) , (Y, σ) , and (Z, γ) always mean topological spaces on which no separation axioms are assumed unless explicitly stated. Let A be a subset of a space X . The closure of A and interior of A are denoted by $\text{cl}(A)$ and $\text{int}(A)$ respectively. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **regularly-open** [7] if it is the interior of its own closure or, equivalently, if it is the interior of some closed sets or equivalently, $A = \text{int}(\text{cl}(A))$. A subset A is said to be **regularly-closed** [7] if it is the closure of its own interior or, equivalently, if it is the closure of some open sets or equivalently, $A = \text{cl}(\text{int}(A))$. Clearly, a set is

regularly-open iff its complement is regularly-closed. The finite union of regularly open sets is said to be π -open. The complement of a π -open set is said to be π -closed. Every regularly open (resp. regularly closed) set is π -open (resp. π -closed).

2.1 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{S}) is said to be

- (i) **generalized closed** (briefly **g-closed**) [8] if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and $U \in \mathfrak{S}$.
- (ii) **regular generalized closed** (briefly **rg-closed**) [12] if $cl(A) \subset U$ whenever $A \subset U$ and U is regular-open in X .

The complement of a g -closed (resp. rg -closed) set is said to be **g-open** (resp. **rg-open**).

The family of all Q^* -closed (resp. Q^* -open) sets of a space X is denoted by $Q^*C(X)$ (resp. $Q^*O(X)$).

The **generalized closure** of A is defined as the intersection of all g -closed sets in X containing A and is denoted by $cl^*(A)$. The **generalized interior** of A is defined as the union of all g -open sets in X contained in A and is denoted by $int^*(A)$.

2.2 Definition. A subset A of a space (X, \mathfrak{S}) is said to be **Q^* -closed** [11] if $int(A) = \phi$ and A is closed. The complement of a Q^* -closed set is said to be **Q^* -open**.

2.3 Definition. The **δ -interior** of a subset A of X is the union of all regular open sets of X contained in A and is denoted by $\delta-int(A)$. The subset A is called **δ -open** [18] if $\delta-int(A) = A$. i.e. a set is δ -open if it is the union of regular open sets, the complement of a δ -open set is called **δ -closed**. Alternatively, a set $A \subset X$ is δ -closed if $A = \delta-cl(A)$, where $\delta-cl(A)$ is the intersection of all regular closed sets of (X, \mathfrak{S}) containing A .

2.4 Definition. Let (X, \mathfrak{S}) be a topological space. A subset A of (X, \mathfrak{S}) is called **regular*-open** [13] (or r^* -open) if $A = int(cl^*(A))$. The complement of a regular*-open set is called **regular*-closed**. The union of all regular*-open sets of X contained in A is called **regular*-interior** and is denoted by $r^*-int(A)$. The intersection of all regular*-closed sets of X containing A is called **regular*-closure** and is denoted by $r^*-cl(A)$.

2.5 Definition. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{S}) is called **η^* -open** [9] set if it is a union of regular*-open sets (r^* -open sets). The complement of a η^* -open set is called **η^* -closed**. A subset A of a topological space (X, \mathfrak{S}) is called **η^* -Interior** of A is the union of all η^* -open sets of X contained in A and is denoted by $\eta^*-int(A)$. The intersection of all η^* -closed sets of X containing A is called as the **η^* -closure** of A and is denoted by $\eta^*-cl(A)$.

2.6 Remark.

- (i) regular closed $\Rightarrow \pi$ -closed $\Rightarrow \delta$ -closed $\Rightarrow \eta^*$ -closed \Rightarrow closed $\Rightarrow g$ -closed $\Rightarrow rg$ -closed

2.7 Remark. For every subset U of X ,

- (i) $g-cl(U) \subset cl(U) \subset \eta^*-cl(U) \subset \delta-cl(U) \subset \pi-cl(U) \subset r-cl(U)$.

2.8 Remark. We have the following implications for the properties of subsets:

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc}
 \text{regular closed} & \Rightarrow & \pi\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \eta^*\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \text{closed} \\
 \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow & & \Downarrow \\
 Q^*\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \text{closed} & \Rightarrow & g\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & \pi g\text{-closed} & \Rightarrow & rg\text{-closed}
 \end{array}$$

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

2.9 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{S} = \{\phi, X, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}\}$. Then

- (i) regular closed sets are : $\phi, X, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (ii) π -closed sets are : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (iii) closed sets are : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (iv) Q^* -closed sets are : $\phi, \{c\}$.
- (v) g -closed sets are : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (vi) πg -closed sets are : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (vii) rg -closed sets are : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.
- (viii) η^* -closed sets are : $\phi, X, \{c\}, \{a, c\}, \{b, c\}$.

2.10 Example. In R with usual metric, finite sets are Q^* -closed but not regular closed. $[0, 1]$ is regular closed but not Q^* -closed. Hence regular closed and Q^* -closed sets are independent of each other.

2.11 Definition. A space X is said to be a **Urysohn space** [17] if for every pair of distinct points x and y , there exist open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $y \in V$ and $cl(U) \cap cl(V) = \phi$.

2.12 Definition. A space X is said to **symmetric space** (or **R_0 -space**) [1] if for any two distinct points x and y of X , $x \in cl(\{y\})$ implies that $y \in cl(\{x\})$.

2.13 Definition. A topological space X is called **T_{η^*} -space** if every η^* -closed set in it is closed set.

2.14 Definition. A space X is said to be **η^* -normal** if for every pair of disjoint η^* -closed subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

2.15 Definition. A space X is said to be **g -normal** [10] (resp. **strongly rg -normal** [3], **Q^* -normal** [5]) if for every pair of disjoint g -closed (resp. rg -closed, Q^* -closed) subsets A, B of X , there exist disjoint open sets U, V of X such that $A \subset U$ and $B \subset V$.

III. Q^* -regular spaces

3.1 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **η^* -regular** if for every η^* -closed set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

3.2 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **Q^* -regular** [6] (resp. **softly regular** [4], **almost regular** [14], **g -regular** [10], **strongly rg -regular** [3]) if for every Q^* -closed (resp. π -closed, regularly closed, g -closed, rg -closed) set A and a point $x \notin A$, there exist disjoint open sets U and V such that $x \in U$, $A \subset V$, and $U \cap V = \phi$.

3.3 Definition. A space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is said to be **semi-regular** [16] if for each point x of the space and each open set U containing x , there is an open set V such that $x \in V \subset int(cl(V)) \subset U$.

3.4 Theorem. Every regular space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Let X be a regular space. Let F be any η^* -closed set in X and a point $x \in X$ such that $x \notin F$. Since we know that every η^* -closed set is closed. So, F is closed and $x \notin F$. Since X is a regular space, there exists a pair of disjoint open sets G and H such that $F \subset G$ and $x \in H$. Hence X is a η^* -regular space.

3.5 Theorem [10]. Every g -regular space is regular hence η^* -regular.

3.6 Theorem [3]. Every strongly rg -regular space is regular hence η^* -regular.

By the definitions and results stated above, we have the following diagram:

Where none of the implications is reversible as can be seen from the following examples:

3.7 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b, c\}, X\}$. Consider the closed set $\{b, c\}$ and a point 'a' such that $a \notin \{b, c\}$. Then $\{b, c\}$ and $\{a\}$ are disjoint open sets such that $\{b, c\} \subset \{b, c, a \in \{a\}$ and $\{b, c\} \cap \{a\} = \phi$. Similarly, for the closed set $\{a\}$ and a point 'c' such that $c \notin \{a\}$. Then there exist open sets $\{a\}$ and $\{b, c\}$ such that $\{a\} \subset \{a, c \in \{b, c\}$ and $\{a\} \cap \{b, c\} = \phi$. It follows that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is regular as well as softly regular space.

3.8 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. If we take a point 'a' and an open set $V = \{a\}$, then $cl(V) = \{a, c\}$ and a regularly-open set $U = X$. So by the definition of weakly regular space $x \in V \subset cl(V) \subset U$, where V be an open set and U be a regularly-open set such that $a \in \{a\} \subset \{a, c\} \subset X$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is weakly regular. If we take a point 'a' and a regularly-closed set $A = \{b, c\}$ does not containing the point 'a',

there donot exist disjoint open sets containing the point ‘a’ and a regularly-closed set $A = \{b, c\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not almost-regular.

3.9 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is weakly regular but not partly-regular. If we take a point ‘a’ and an open set $V = \{a\}$, then $\text{cl}(V) = \{a, c\}$. Let $U = \{a, b\}$ be any π -open set. So by the definition of partly-regular space $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$, where V be an open set and U be a π -open set such that $a \in \{a\} \subset \{a, c\} \not\subset \{a, b\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not partly-regular.

3.10 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{b\}, \{a, b\}, X\}$. Then (X, \mathfrak{T}) is weakly regular but not softly-regular. Let $A = \{c\}$ be any π -closed set doesnot containing a point ‘a’ i.e. $a \notin \{c\}$, there do not exist disjoint open sets containing the point ‘a’ and the π -closed set $A = \{c\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not softly-regular.

3.11 Example. Let $X = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $\mathfrak{T} = \{\phi, \{a\}, \{a, b\}, \{a, b, c\}, \{a, b, d\}, X\}$. Then the space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is almost regular but not strongly rg-regular. If we take a point ‘a’ and $F = \{b\}$ be any rg-closed set. Then there do not exist disjoint open sets containing the point ‘a’ and rg-closed set $F = \{b\}$. Hence (X, \mathfrak{T}) is not strongly rg-regular.

IV. Properties of η^* -regular spaces

4.1 Theorem. For a topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) , the following properties are equivalent:

- (a) (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η^* -regular.
- (b) For every $x \in X$ and every η^* -open set U containing x , there exists an open set V such that $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$.
- (c) For every η^* -closed set A , the intersection of all the closed neighbourhood of A is A .
- (d) For every set A and a η^* -open set B such that $A \cap B \neq \phi$, there exists an open set F such that $A \cap F \neq \phi$ and $\text{cl}(F) \subset B$.
- (e) For every nonempty set A and η^* -closed set B such that $A \cap B = \phi$, there exist disjoint open sets L and M such that $A \cap L \neq \phi$ and $B \subset M$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Suppose (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η^* -regular. Let $x \in X$ and U be a η^* -open set containing x so that $X - U$ is η^* -closed. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η^* -regular, there exist open sets V_1 and V_2 such that $V_1 \cap V_2 = \phi$ and $x \in V_1, X - U \subset V_2$. Take $V = V_1$. Since $V_1 \cap V_2 = \phi, V \subset X - V_2 \subset U$ that implies $\text{cl}(V) \subset \text{cl}(X - V_2) = X - V_2 \subset U$. Therefore $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset U$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Let A be η^* -closed set and $x \notin A$. Since A is η^* -closed, $X - A$ is η^* -open and $x \in X - A$. Therefore by (b) there exists an open set V such that $x \in V \subset \text{cl}(V) \subset X - A$. Thus $A \subset X - \text{cl}(V) \subset X - V$ and $x \notin X - V$. Consequently $X - V$ is a closed neighborhood of A .

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Let $A \cap B \neq \phi$ and B be η^* -open. Let $x \in A \cap B$. Since B is η^* -open, $X - B$ is η^* -closed and $x \notin X - B$. By our assumption, there exists a closed neighborhood V of $X - B$ such that $x \notin V$. Let $X - B \subset U \subset V$, where U is open. Then $F = X - V$ is open such that $x \in F$ and $A \cap F \neq \emptyset$. Also $X - U$ is closed and $\text{cl}(F) = \text{cl}(X - V) \subset X - U \subset B$. This shows that $\text{cl}(F) \subset B$.

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Suppose $A \cap B = \phi$, where A is non-empty and B is η^* -closed. Then $X - B$ is η^* -open and $A \cap (X - B) \neq \phi$. By (d), there exists an open set L such that $A \cap L \neq \phi$, and $L \subset \text{cl}(L) \subset X - B$. Put $M = X - \text{cl}(L)$. Then $B \subset M$ and L, M are open sets such that $M = X - \text{cl}(L) \subset (X - L)$.

(e) \Rightarrow (a). Let B be η^* -closed and $x \notin B$. Then $B \cap \{x\} = \phi$. By (e), there exist disjoint open sets L and M such that $L \cap \{x\} \neq \phi$ and $B \subset M$. Since $L \cap \{x\} \neq \phi, x \in L$. This proves that (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η^* -regular.

4.2 Theorem. A topological space (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η^* -regular if and only if for each η^* -closed set F of (X, \mathfrak{T}) and each $x \in X - F$, there exist open sets U and V of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in U$ and $F \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \phi$.

Proof: Let F be a η^* -closed set in (X, \mathfrak{T}) and $x \notin F$. Then there exist open sets U_x and V such that $x \in U_x, F \subset V$ and $U_x \cap V = \phi$. This implies that $U_x \cap \text{cl}(V) = \phi$. Since $\text{cl}(V)$ is closed and $x \notin \text{cl}(V)$. Since (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η^* -regular, there exist open sets G and H of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in G, \text{cl}(V) \subset H$ and $G \cap H = \phi$. This implies $\text{cl}(G) \cap$

$H = \phi$. Take $U = U_x \cap G$. Then U and V are open sets of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in U$ and $F \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \phi$, since $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) \subset \text{cl}(G) \cap H = \phi$.

Conversely, suppose for each η^* -closed set F of (X, \mathfrak{T}) and each $x \in X - F$, there exist open sets U and V of (X, \mathfrak{T}) such that $x \in U$, $F \subset V$ and $\text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \phi$. Now $U \cap V \subset \text{cl}(U) \cap \text{cl}(V) = \phi$. Therefore $U \cap V = \phi$. Thus (X, \mathfrak{T}) is η^* -regular.

4.3 Theorem. In a η^* -regular space X , every pair consisting of a compact set A and a disjoint η^* -closed set B can be separated by open sets.

Proof. Let X be η^* -regular space and let A be a compact set, B be a η^* -closed set with $A \cap B = \phi$. Since X is η^* -regular space, for each $x \in A$, there exist disjoint open sets U_x and V_x such that $x \in U_x$, $B \subset V_x$. Clearly $\{U_x : x \in A\}$ is an open covering of the compact set A . Since A is compact, there exists a finite subfamily $\{U_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ which covers A . It follows that $A \subset \cup \{U_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ and $B \subset \cap \{V_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$. Put $U = \cup \{U_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$ and $V = \cap \{V_{x_i} : i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, n\}$, then $U \cap V = \phi$. For, if $x \in U \cap V \Rightarrow x \in U_{x_j}$ for some j and $x \in V_{x_i}$ for every i . This implies that $x \in U_{x_j} \cap V_{x_i}$, which is a contradiction to $U_{x_j} \cap V_{x_i} = \phi$. Thus U and V are disjoint open sets containing A and B respectively.

V. Relationships of η^* -regular spaces with Some Separation Axioms

5.1 Theorem [14]. Every almost regular, semi-regular space is regular.

5.2 Corollary. Every almost regular, semi-regular space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every regular space is η^* -regular.

5.3 Corollary. Every softly regular, semi-regular space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every softly regular space is almost regular.

5.4 Theorem [1]. Every normal, symmetric space is regular.

5.5 Corollary. Every normal, symmetric space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every regular space is η^* -regular.

5.6 Corollary. Every g -normal, symmetric space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every g -normal space is normal.

5.7 Corollary. Every rg -normal, symmetric space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every rg -normal space is normal.

5.8 Theorem [15]. Every compact Hausdorff space is regular.

5.9 Corollary. Every compact Hausdorff space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every regular space is η^* -regular.

5.10 Corollary. Every compact Urysohn space is η^* -regular.

Proof. Using the fact that every Urysohn space is Hausdorff.

VI. Conclusion.

In this paper, we introduce and study a new class of generalized regular space is called η^* -regular space which is weaker than regularity. The relationships among strongly rg -regular, g -regular, regular, Q^* -regular, η^* -regular, almost regular and softly regular spaces are investigated. Some of basic properties and characterizations of η^* -regular spaces in the terms of other separation and countability axioms such as semi-regular, Hausdorff, separable, second countable and Lindelof spaces are obtained. This idea can be extended to topological ordered, bitopological, bitopological ordered and fuzzy topological spaces etc.

Acknowledgement : The author is thankful to Dr. M. C. Sharma, NREC College Khurja, U. P. for his valuable suggestions and encouragement throughout preparation of this article.

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